

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D6.3 Dissemination and communication activities v2

WP6 - Dissemination and Communication

Version: 1.00

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Document information

Grant Agreement Number	873134	Acronym	CALIPER
Full Title	The CALIPER project: Linking research and innovation for gender equality		
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans		
Funding scheme	CSA – Coordination and Support Action		
Start Date	1 st January 2020	Duration	48 months
Project URL	http://caliper-project.eu/		
EU Project Officer	Katharina Buse, REA, Unit B5		
Project Coordinator	Vasiliki Moumtzi – ViLabs Kyriaki Karydou - ViLabs		
Deliverable	D6.3. Dissemination and communication activities v2		
Work Package	WP6 – Dissemination and communication		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M30	Actual M30
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P - Public
Lead Beneficiary	VILABS		
Responsible Author (s)	Danai Kyrkou (ViLabs) Kyriaki Karydou (ViLbas)		
Reviewer(s):	Cardiff University (CU)		
Keywords	Dissemination, communication		

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.10	23/06/22	Draft	Draft ready for internal review	VIL
0.20	29/06/22	Draft	Updated version	VIL, CU, STUBA
1.00	30/06/22	Final	Ready for submission	ViLabs

Executive Summary

The project's dissemination and communication activities constitute a pivotal aspect of its overall design, given their role in promoting CALIPER's contributions toward gender equality. The project has adopted a multifaceted and detailed dissemination plan implemented via a set of concrete actions from the very beginning in order to:

- Raise awareness about the CALIPER project
- Increase engagement and encourage the involvement of the target groups in the project activities.
- Promote sustainability actions and best practices of CALIPER actions after the project's completion.

The unprecedented global conditions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, have become less restrictive throughout the past months, allowing the partners to organise events and activities in physical presence as well as online. In this respect, the present deliverable describes the progress by providing statistics on the dissemination and communication activities, performed both online and offline from April 2021 until June 2022 (M16-M30) by the CALIPER partners. The report presents the actions taken by the Consortium Members as applied examples of the ways that the objectives of the Project's dissemination strategy can be deployed. It features the following:

- data regarding the project website and the social media channels created for CALIPER,
- networking activities of the Consortium Members and all the additional actions taken to promote the project and its scope (i.e., press releases, newsletters, videos and interviews, events etc.).
- progress report of the KPIs

This is the second of three versions of the Dissemination and Communication Activities report (M15, M30 and M48).

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
GEPs	Gender Equality Plans
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
UZG - FER	University of Zagreb - Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering
MTF STU BA	Faculty of Materials Science and Technology - Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
ECE - NTUA	School of Electrical & Computer engineering - National Technical University of Athens
IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine in Barcelona
YU	Yasar University
UNILE	Salento University
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
UEFISCDI	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania
YAE	Young Academy of Europe

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The present deliverable is the second report of the activities implemented by the project partners to disseminate and communicate CALIPER. It presents the progress and results of the CALIPER dissemination and communication strategy for the period M16-M30 (April 2021 – June 2022). Also, it analyses the progress of the communication strategy, and suggests how the next steps of the dissemination action plan should follow.

In this regard, the present report includes the following:

- Actions aimed at optimising the dissemination and communication tools
- Progress report on the communication channels and activities, both online and offline
- Progress report on the KPIs

1.2 Target Audience

This report is aimed for all project partners to further develop/implement their individual and collaborative activities, as well as to identify needs and re-adjust the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy. In addition, the document can be used as a guide and practical tool for “Horizon2020” – “Horizon Europe” dissemination managers of on-going and future projects, who may be willing to explore the CALIPER strategy and capitalise on it, as well as a guide/control point for the reviewers of the European Commission. Lastly, the current deliverable can be used by anyone who wishes to replicate the CALIPER dissemination approach.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured into the following sections: Chapter 1 introduces the document's target audience, the relationship to the other work packages and the structure. Chapter 2 describes the updates on the CALIPER website. Chapter 3 provides information on the activities that have been taken place during the reporting period, as well as their outreach. It also includes information about the synergies of CALIPER with other projects and initiatives. Chapter 4 presents the “Monitoring and Evaluation” of the KPIs, and chapter 5 presents the next steps.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The activities presented in this deliverable draw from and feed back into the overall actions of the project. In addition, this deliverable is closely interlinked with ‘WP5 - Engagement, change management and sustainability’ by sharing mutual objectives in terms of stakeholders’ engagement.

2 Optimisation of the Dissemination and Communication Tools (M16-M30)

This chapter provides information about the optimisation of the dissemination and communication tools of CALIPER. In this reporting period, the deliverable presents the updates on the project website.

2.1 CALIPER Website updates

The [CALIPER website](#) went live on March 2020, the third month of the project. Since the last reporting period, there have been some improvements of the website to boost its efficiency. It is the major source of the project's identity, goals and actions, on which every stakeholder group can be informed. The CALIPER website operates as a central dissemination and communication tool for the project by providing the main results of the Consortium's efforts. In particular, the CALIPER website is used to:

- Provide information about the project, its main objectives, descriptions of the Gender Equality Plans and the activities carried out for their design and implementation, publications, latest news and upcoming events in which CALIPER will participate, information about the involved RPOs/RFOs and descriptions of related projects with a link to their websites, press releases, subscription to the project's newsletter, communication material, social networks and contact info.
- Present information to stakeholders so that they will understand the reasons to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities.
- Provide a common reference point for interested stakeholders to access all the content produced in the project, including the partners' GEPs.

In order to optimise the user experience, the following updates are reported:

1. In the page "About" the user can now find the extra sub-page "[Contact us](#)" with the project contact details and the names of the project coordinator and the communication manager. This information allows every interested visitor to contact us for further information about the project and engage more in the CALIPER activities. Also, there is a point of reference in case someone wants to report any issues with the website.

Figure 1 CALIPER page "contact us"

2. In each RPO/RFO's sub-page under the page "[Gender Equality Action](#)", the user can find information about the RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER project. Each partner RPO/RFO has a unique page that presents the profile of the organisation, an assessment of gender equality status inside the organisation and in its ecosystem, the GEP, a list of the organisation's staff who are engaged with CALIPER (GEP Working Groups and the organisational team) and a sub-section where the implemented activities are presented. As the project goes on, the goal is to enrich the pages of the partners as much as possible to communicate their work with the external stakeholders. In this vein, the communication manager is in the process of updating the pages with additional content about the Research & Innovation Hubs the organisations have created, and the material they have produced from their GEP (toolkits, guides, etc.). This is work in progress, so the updates follow from receipt of the available material from the partners. The final version of these updates will be provided in the final deliverable D6.4 in M48.

The dissemination and communication strategy of CALIPER is an ongoing process that the communication manager evaluates periodically in order to optimise its effectiveness. The reach of the communication tools and channels is also assessed to understand if the strategy works and to adapt the content accordingly.

3 Reporting of the dissemination activities and statistics

During the reporting period of the deliverable, the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs have completed the design and development phase and approval of their GEPs and started the implementation of the respective actions. All the dissemination and communication activities that have been taken place throughout this period targeted key external stakeholders to inform them about these activities and engage them to the foreseen actions.

The dissemination of the plans aims at ensuring internal and external commitment of key stakeholders to facilitate the implementation and the sustainability of the tailored GEP for each CALIPER partner.

This chapter maps the communication channels' progress during the respective reporting period. It includes metrics from the website and the social media accounts, the external activities the consortium has participated in, the newsletters, and the promotion of CALIPER through partners' networks.

3.1 CALIPER website

The CALIPER website is one of the key resources used for the dissemination activities of CALIPER towards its target audiences. During this reporting period, the goal was to expand the visibility and the reach of the dissemination and communication tools and channels. Google Analytics allowed the mapping of the traffic by tracking the numbers of the visitors and other relevant metrics over the last 15 months of the project.

The figures below, display the results from this reporting period, from M16 to M30.

User acquisition

Starting with the website performance, based on the Google Analytics tool, the first category we observe is the "user acquisition", to obtain an overview of our users' behaviour when they visit the project website.

Figure 2 Google analytics – CALIPER website

According to figure 2, during the reporting period the CALIPER website had 5,021 new users, 7,321 sessions, 15,942 page views, 1.45 sessions per user, 2.18 pages per session, an average session duration of 2m06s and a bounce rate of 63.61%. The communication manager assesses these numbers regularly and tracks the website's shortcomings to find the most efficient way for its optimisation.

An explanation of terms is available below:

- *Users: A person browsing the website (technically, a unique browser cookie)*
- *New users: The number of users who interacted with your site or launched your app for the first time (event-triggered: first open).*
- *Sessions: A single visit to your website, consisting of one or more page views, along with events, e-commerce transactions, and other interactions*
- *Number of sessions per user: The average number of sessions per user.*
- *Pageviews: The total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.*
- *Pages/Session (Average Page Depth): The average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted.*
- *Average session duration: The average length of time that the app was in the foreground, or the website had a focus in the browser.*
- *Bounce rate: The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. A bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds.*

Table 1 Term explanation – Google analytics

Demographics

In terms of visitors' demographics, the following figure lists the countries of audience's origin. Traffic comes both from countries of the project's consortium and countries around the world, showing the outreach of the website beyond the countries of the directly involved parties. Overall, the communication manager works on increasing the incoming visitors, both new and returning ones, putting more effort in the countries represented in the project.

Country ?	Acquisition
	Users ? ↓
	5,064 % of Total: 100.00% (5,064)
1. United States	538 (10.56%)
2. Greece	423 (8.31%)
3. Belgium	365 (7.17%)
4. Spain	316 (6.20%)
5. Netherlands	312 (6.13%)
6. China	286 (5.62%)
7. Croatia	271 (5.32%)
8. Italy	242 (4.75%)
9. United Kingdom	181 (3.55%)
10. Romania	177 (3.48%)

Figure 3 Website demographics: Country of origin

The demographic statistics about website visitors show a fairly balanced gender distribution with 54.15% male users and 45.85% female users. Also, more than half of the users (61%) are between 18 and 34 years old, meaning, the website is mostly visited by young adults.

Figure 4 Website demographics: Gender and age

Pages and screens

Another important piece of information refers to the most popular pages. By tracking them, the communication manager can understand what the visitors are more interested in and organise a more efficient communication plan. On the other hand, by knowing the least popular pages, they can work on promoting them more and attract traffic.

Figure 5 Website: Popular pages

The most popular page is the home page with 5,336 views. According to the figure above, the project vision and the role model videos page have also attracted more users (932 and 571 views respectively). Also, four of the 9 RPOs/RFOs are in the first 10 most popular pages (ULB, UZG-FER, SRNSFG, ECE-NTUA). This shows the interest towards the organisations that implement the CALIPER GEPs.

Overall, the numbers can be raised in the next reporting period. This can be done by connecting more the content CALIPER posts on social media, to links that direct the user to the website. As a result, the traffic will be increased.

3.2 Social media and online channels

The social media channels enable dissemination and communication of the CALIPER activities, enhancing the project's outreach, and work as the key info point and a point of reference even at the project's website. This section aims to present the impact of CALIPER social media and the results of this reporting period (M16-M30) per social media channel. Furthermore, social media is used for interacting with various target groups such as other EU funded projects working on gender equality, EU policymakers, and other interested parties working on this sector.

3.2.1 Twitter

The [Twitter account of CALIPER](#) currently counts 415 followers. The account is used to spread key messages about the project such as significant developments on the preparation of Gender Equality Plans, dissemination material such as video interviews, partners' participation in events, awareness campaigns by relevant EU-funded projects and gender equality and science news. Due to the nature of the platform and the character limit in the posts, the messages are very concrete without many details, with an aim to catch the attention of the followers through short on point messages. It has become the most popular social media channel in terms of engagement, since the majority of the sister projects, as well as the researchers and managers working on them, are active on Twitter.

Figure 6 CALIPER Twitter account

The communication manager updates the Twitter page frequently and uses relevant hashtags to amplify the information dissemination. Examples of these hashtags include #EU, #h2020, #GenderEquality, #innovation,

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#research #STEM etc. Also, the rest of the partners have shared their twitter accounts, so that the communication manager can tag them in relevant tweets and let them retweet the content.

To evaluate the course of CALIPER's Twitter account, the Analytics portal of the platform has been examined for valuable insights. As a result, data from April 2021 until the current month of the project, June 2022, are presented. Since Twitter divides the reporting periods into trimesters, we added up the periods separately. The overall numbers for M16-M30 are presented in Table 1 below. The CALIPER Twitter account has a total of 105.5K impressions, with an engagement rate of 3.4% per post:

Impressions	105.7K (total)
Engagement	2,503 (total)
Engagement rate	3.4% (average)

Table 2 Twitter metrics

- *Impressions: The times the post came across a user's feed*
- *Engagement: The times a single user interacted with the post (like, retweet, comment. Click on link)*

Table 3 Twitter terms

Given the number of followers (415) and the number of impressions (105.7K), it seems that the posts have a significantly wider reach, which is justified by the popularity of the platform.

3.2.2 Facebook

The [CALIPER Facebook page](#), like all the social media accounts of CALIPER is mainly used to post content that is sourced on the project's website, such as project's news and/or announcements. Facebook gives the ability to provide more information to the user, since there is no character limit in the posts. In this vein, the Facebook posts are more detailed. Currently, the CALIPER Facebook page accounts for 558 followers.

Figure 7 CALIPER Facebook page

To assess the progress of this channel, metrics from Facebook Insights have been used. In terms of demographics, the followers are mostly females (62%). In terms of age, the CALIPER followers belong mainly to young adults (25-34 age group) and middle age cohorts (35-44 & 45-54 age groups).

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Figure 8 Facebook demographics: Gender and age

In terms of geographical distribution, most followers come from the Consortium Members’ countries; mainly from Greece (160) and Italy (148). Based on these statistics, it is deemed necessary to grow the number of followers of the page by gaining more Facebook users from the rest of the countries represented inside the Consortium. To achieve this, the communication manager in collaboration with the partners from these counties can promote more the activities that are taking place there to engage more local actors.

Country	Your Followers
Greece	160
Italy	148
Belgium	58
Georgia	54
Spain	13
Turkey	13
Croatia	12
United Kingdom	6
Romania	6
Germany	5

Figure 9 Facebook demographics: Country of origin

Other noteworthy insights are the “engagement” and the “reach”. In the figure 10 below it seems that posts that include images have the widest reach (168 on average) to the followers and wide engagement (21 on average). In addition, the posts that include video clips also have great reach (110). More importantly, they are quite engaging for the audience, since they have less reach than the posts with photos but the same engagement numbers (21 in total). Considering the performance of the different types of posts, the project will keep updating its Facebook page with diverse content to keep its followers engaged.

- “Reach”: The number of users that came across a post
- “Engagement”: The times a user interacts with a post. This includes clicks on the post, likes, reshares, and comments.

Table 4 Facebook terms

Figure 10 Facebook posts' reach & engagement per post type

3.2.3 LinkedIn

The [LinkedIn](#) page currently counts 181 followers and has been opted for more targeted discussions and information about the project as it is progressing in its implementation.

Figure 11 CALIPER LinkedIn page

The followers of the page come mostly from the sectors of Research (17%) and Education (9%). However, the data show that different people from different backgrounds are interested in the CALIPER page. In the figure 12 below, the 10 most prominent job functions are presented. Also, CALIPER followers come from different places around Europe, with the most from Spain, and Belgium.

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Figure 12 LinkedIn demographics: Job function & Location

In terms of impressions and engagement, the page gained more than 11,600 impressions during this reporting period, with December and May being the months with the best performance. In December the sister projects had a double campaign on #ChristmasWishes4Equality & #NewYearWishes4Equality in which CALIPER participated in, and during May the posts varied including activities with the sister projects, the most recent role model video of CALIPER, and the CALIPER campaign for the Diversity month explaining the abovementioned numbers potentially.

The engagement rate is up to 13.84%, with July, November, March, and April being the months with the highest engagement. The increased traffic in July can be explained by the release of the Georgian role model video of CALIPER, and the posts about the newsletter that was released at that time. In November, many of the CALIPER RPOs/RFOs completed the design and development phase of their GEPs and relevant posts were made, creating more traffic. Last, in March and April the sister projects run a campaign for the International Women’s Day, and several CALIPER activities took place that were promoted on social media.

Figure 13 LinkedIn post impressions

Figure 14 LinkedIn Engagement rate

- “Impressions”: The number of users that came across a post
- “Engagement”: The times a user interacts with a post. This includes clicks on the post, likes, reshares, and comments.

Table 5 LinkedIn terms

3.2.4 YouTube channel

The [YouTube channel of CALIPER](#) contains promotional videos that the RPOs/RFOs created about CALIPER, and the role model videos that are being produced with the context of T6.3.

Figure 15 CALIPER YouTube channel

In total, the 12 uploaded videos have 1,048 views, with the role model videos to be the most popular. More information about them will be provided in the respective deliverable D6.7.

3.3 CALIPER Newsletter

During this reporting period, CALIPER has circulated three newsletter issues to its audience, and currently has 225 subscribers. All newsletter issues can be found on the dedicated [page](#) of the CALIPER website.

[CALIPER 3rd Newsletter Issue – July 2021](#)

Through this newsletter, the project shared news about the publication of the Gender Equality Plans in the nine RPOs/RFOs, promoted the role model videos, and informed readers about the collaborative actions and news of the EU Sister Projects.

Figure 16 Newsletter 3rd issue

CALIPER 4th Newsletter issue – February 2022

In this newsletter, the project included information about the CALIPER events that took place at the time, the consortium's new partner, Cardiff University, and synergy activities with the EU Sister Projects.

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Figure 17 Newsletter 4th issue

CALIPER 5th Newsletter special issue – May 2022

This newsletter issue was specifically dedicated to the release of the most recent role model video of CALIPER. It provided information about the interviewee, the interview itself, as well as the past role model videos for further promotion.

Figure 18 Newsletter 5th special issue

In addition to the project’s newsletter, CALIPER has been featured in newsletter pieces circulated by the CALIPER partners and other organisations. These newsletters will be presented on the “promotion through partners’ network” section.

3.4 Press releases

Throughout the reported period of this deliverable, CALIPER and the partners published 3 press releases that are publicly available at the project’s [website](#).

[SRNSFG | Their approved and published GEP on their institutional website](#) – March 2022

With this press release, SRNSFG announced the completion of the design and development phase of their GEP, as well as described the key steps that were followed through this process.

Figure 19 SRNSFG press release

[CALIPER | The Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub of Cardiff University joins CALIPER – February 2022](#)

This press release was published on [Europa Wire](#), to inform the audience that all CALIPER RPOs/RFOs have completed the design and development phase of their GEP and they are ready to proceed with the implementation of the foreseen actions.

Figure 20 CALIPER press release

[FER-UZG | Gender Equality Status Report 2020 – September 2021](#)

In this press release, UZG-FER announced the result form the Gender Equality report from 2020, based on a survey about the state of gender equality in FER that was organised in the context of CALIPER.

Figure 21 FER-UZG press release

3.4.1 Publications

During this reporting period there was one scientific publication related to CALIPER.

[Setting up inclusive Gender Equality Plans – The CALIPER experience – TBP \(pg.109-110\)](#)

Under the conference “[Diversity interventions 2022](#)” in April 2022, CALIPER submitted an abstract that was accepted and is currently under publication. The material of the abstract is based on the first version of the CALIPER policy briefings on the topic of designing and developing an inclusive GEP.

Short description of the abstract: The adoption of a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) aims at removing the systemic obstacles to Gender Equality (GE) and at adapting institutional practices leaving no one behind. However, there is a need for a renewed approach to the development of a GEP which is reflected in the EC’s new policy direction which is going towards a more inclusive approach. This new direction refers to “inclusive GEPs”, covering 3 aspects: intersectionality, intersectoriality, and geographic inclusiveness. Elaborating on these

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dimensions, the aim of the publication is to present below the CALIPER methodology and provide practical examples for setting up inclusive GEPs.

Authors: Kyriaki Karydou (VIL), Maria Sangiuliano (SV), Vicky Moutzi (VIL), Danai Kyrkou (VIL), Marzia Cescon (SV)

[“Women in Innovation”](#)

During the FER-WIN event, the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of the University of Zagreb, published the book “Women in Innovation”, which gives a brief overview of the socio-historical context of women’s inclusion in the scientific and educational system and presents the first seven scientists in the field of electrical engineering who worked at the faculty until 1970. These are: Prof. dr. sc. Višnja Henč-Bartolić, M.Sc. Marica Jurišić-Zec, Ph.D. dr. sc. Vesna Kos, Ph.D. dr. sc. Jasna Šimunić-Hrvoić, M.Sc. sc. Mirjana Urbiha-Feuerbach, M.Sc. sc. Kalma Zimmermann-Pavčević and Prof. dr. sc. Branka Zovko-Cihlar. From the historical context the reader can see what challenges they faced in their professional and scientific path and what factors influenced their empowerment.

Authors: Marijanović, Branka; Milišić, Josipa Pina; Nakić, Anamari

The book is available [here](#).

3.4.2 Articles and interviews

During this reporting period there were 7 activities that covered non peer reviewed publications, podcasts, and interviews.

[“GEP in Horizon 2020 – Opportunity for Inclusion and Wellbeing”](#)

STU BA, participated in the Final CHANGE Stakeholder International Workshop, and submitted the paper “GEP in Horizon 2020 – Opportunity for Inclusion and Wellbeing”. The workshop was organised by the sister project [CHANGE](#) and took place in Aveiro, Portugal on the 26th and 27th of April 2022. The article presents the H2020 project “Linking Research and Innovation with Focus on Gender Equality” (acronym CALIPER) and its practices. The aim is to make research organisations more gender equal by promoting a greater engagement of female researchers in STEM and stimulating dialogue and collaboration between academia, public authorities, professionals, and industry players in order to overcome and tackle gender inequalities across the research transfer to the market chain.

Authors: Dagmar Cagáňová, Natália Horňáková, Ľubica Znamenáková, Filip Majtán

[The CALIPER project and the ULB STEM Gender Equality Plan on Radio Campus](#)

The ULB team of the CALIPER project gave an interview on Radio Campus on December 13, 2021, in the context of the programme “Histoire de Savoir”. The guests talked about gender stereotypes in STEM and the initiatives put in place by the University to encourage girls to pursue studies in STEM and support women in their scientific careers in these fields. The actions undertaken by the university were organised in the context of the CALIPER project.

[Prof. Dagmar Cagáňová on the SPEKTRUM 2021/2022 #1–2 / ŽENA VO VEDE: Cez prekážky ku hviezdám / Through barriers towards the stars](#)

Prof. Dagmar Cagáňová from STU BA gave an interview for the magazine of the Slovak Technical University of Bratislava and talked about CALIPER, its goals and the vision for gender equality in the STEM field. Dagmar talked about her work in CALIPER and the importance of gender equality, not only internally in the research

institutions, but also in the local research and innovation ecosystems. The GEP eligibility criterion from the European Commission, was an opportunity to promote innovation inside and out of the organisation. The interviewer asked Dagmar when she realised that the issue of gender equality was important, and she talked about the example of her family and children and the disproportionate burden that lies on women in terms of caregiving.

[ŽensCast#5: Prof. Emerita Branka Zovko Cihlar – Interview](#)

On the occasion of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, in the fifth edition of ŽensCast, UZG-FER spoke with Professor Emeritus Branka Zovko Cihlar. Professor Zovko Cihlar received her PhD from the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Zagreb in 1964, as the first female Doctor of Electrical Engineering in Croatia. She revealed how she developed an interest in electrical engineering and pointed out that for her, the greatest success are the happy and satisfied people whom she encouraged as a mentor to find themselves in scientific and teaching work at FER. The professor was very proud of her former students and doctoral students, today engineers and scientists, who with their work actively contribute to the progress of FER and the betterment of society as a whole.

[“We asked the rector, the dean and the top scientist what it is like to be a woman in science”](#)

On the occasion of the International Women Day, the Dean of the Faculty of Informatics and Organisation of UZG, Nina Begičević Ređep, mentioned CALIPER during her interview. She talked about what we specifically need in order to influence the unequal position of women in science. She said that they lack activities and projects whose results would affect the position of women in science as well as motivating girls from an early age to decide on a scientific career. According to the Dean, one of the positive initiatives is CALIPER, within a number of activities and new projects which have been initiated by Professor Anamari Nakić. Finally, she believes that it is necessary to sensitise the public to the issue of gender equality, and all this should be accompanied by an appropriate legal framework.

[Media coverage of YU WIN Event \(newspaper articles in 9 different print media\)](#)

After the WIN event that Yasar University held in the context of the engagement activities of their GEP, the local and national newspapers hosted news articles about it. In the articles there was a description of the CALIPER project and more specifically, about the WIN event and its purpose. Appr. 1,000,000 people become aware of the project both published and online news articles.

3.4.3 Social media campaign by CALIPER

May was the European Diversity Month and CALIPER project organised a campaign with the participating RPOs/RFOs to celebrate it. The dissemination material posted during this campaign was based on two questions:

- *What does embracing diversity means to you?*
- *What can academic community do to end discrimination?*

Stakeholders from the consortium such as researchers, academics, administrative staff, and students, had the opportunity to answer these questions and share their views. The quotes were put in a poster and the communication manager made relevant posts on social media. The posters and some sample posts can be found below:

#calipereu

Education within a diverse environment helps students to develop critical thinking inside and outside the campus. It encourages mutual respect and synergy. Diversity, equity, and inclusion are making students better scholars, co-workers and citizens.

- Maro (ECE-NTUA)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

#calipereu

The role of academia is to educate young people and show example to students that all people are equal even though some people are different or have different needs.

- STU BA colleagues

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

#calipereu

The academic community has the commitment to eliminate all forms of discrimination leading by the example, implementing good practices and providing the students and personnel with a safe and supportive environment.

- IRB colleagues

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

#calipereu

The academic community needs to develop good practices to combat discrimination and engage with policymakers to implement them. We need to expose underlying social norms and lead strategic advocacy to combat discriminatory practices and policies in and outside academia and advocate for "leave no one behind" approach by addressing the root causes of inequality.

- SRNSFG colleagues

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

#calipereu

*"Embracing diversity means...
...to respect the differences that are not easily seen or understood."*

- Maro (ECE-NTUA)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

#calipereu

*"Embracing diversity means...
...that each individual is unique, respected and accepted by everyone in the society.
...to promote ways to foster and maintain an environment that is socially inclusive and welcomes diversity.
... to boost innovation and success.*

- IRB colleagues

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

Figure 22 EU Diversity month CALIPER material

Figure 23 EU Diversity month sample posts

3.4.4 Events organised by CALIPER

During this reporting period, the CALIPER partners organised 8 events. A short description of them can be found below:

RETE: Questioni di genere

Date: 26 March – 24 May 2021 | Location: Salento, Italy | Partner: UNILE

In spring 2021 UNILE hosted a very interesting exhibition that lasted approximately two months and addressed various topics around gender equality. These topics include:

- Climate change and gender
- Contemporary feminist politics, keywords: Society of care
- Contemporary feminist politics, keywords: Vulnerability
- For a debate on language and political communication in Italy. The role of the Constituent Mothers

- Language and gender, language of gender. Extralinguistic profiles and methodological issues from texts and contexts from the public and institutional domain
- Sexism and stereotypes in the media
- Discovering women in early Christianity
- The ‘beautiful prisoner’ from the Bible to the Middle Ages
- Women and the family in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Philosophical reflection and utopian perspective
- Deconstructing gender imagery
- An experience of teaching gender history. The project “Women’s traces in school archives”.
- Between role and freedom, the space of women in Greek culture
- Examples of femininity in Plautus and on the threshold of the Principate
- Women’s evolutionary process: from invisibility to identity awareness
- Women in a world of (super)men: underwater archaeologists
- For your eyes only’: when women become things
- Smart working and work-life balance: the perspective of women at work
- Gender-based violence, memory, re-enactment and habituation: a psychological and psychophysiological analysis, also in relation to the pandemic period

This exhibition was an attempt to sensitise the audience and inform them about the structural inequalities around gender, portraying the need for change and redefinition. The event was co-organised by UNILE’s CALIPER team

[UniSalento Open Space](#)

Date: 28-29 October 2021 | Location: Salento, Italy | Partner: UNILE

UNILE organised a cycle of initiatives to promote processes of inclusion and enhancement of differences and combat homobitranphobic discrimination. The initiative by the CUG – Unified Guarantee Committee of the University of Salento is called “UniSalento open space”, in collaboration with the Association RaNe – Rainbow Network APS and Agedo Lecce. It started on 14 October 2021 and it was intended to investigate “the cultural and psychological reasons that, at times, are at the basis of closed attitudes towards sexual and gender facets, offering tools to recognise stereotypes and to reflect on how these reverberate in individual behaviors”. The event was co-organised by UNILE’s CALIPER team

[“Com’eri vestita?": mostra contro la violenza di genere](#)

Date: 10-18 November 2021 | Location: Salento, Italy | Partner: UNILE

“How were you dressed?": From 10 to 18 November 2021 the traveling exhibition against the stereotypes that blame the victims of rape was hosted at the University of Salento. The idea for this exhibition followed the exhibition “What were you wearing?”, Organised for the first appeared in 2013 by the University of Arkansas Rape Education Center. The exhibition was adapted to the Italian context by the Libera Sinergie Association of Milan and brought to Puglia by the South Association, East Women. In total 148 people attended the exhibition, 134 women and 14 men, mostly from the academia and research sector. The event was co-organised by UNILE’s CALIPER team

[Annual Conference of the National Association of the Equality Bodies of the Italian Universities](#)

Date: 11-12 November 2021 | Location: Salento, Italy (hybrid) | Partner: UNILE

On 11th and 12th November, the Conference of the National Association of Equality Bodies of Italian Universities focused on “*Gender Equality Plans and smart-working: changes in well-being in Academia. Smart*

working from emergency to opportunity". The Conference represented a useful opportunity to share the best practices initiated by various Italian universities for the implementation of smart working, initially dictated by the emergency condition imposed by the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and subsequently by the awareness of the positive impact of the same on the well-being of employees.

[International Conference "Women in Science"](#)

Date: 20 November 2021 | Location: Tbilisi, Georgia | Partner: SRNSFG

On November 20, 2021, Shota Rustaveli Georgian National Science Foundation organised the international conference "Women in Science" within the framework of the 2021 Science Festival and the EU Research and Innovation Framework Program "Horizon 2020". The event was attended by female scientists working in STEM in various higher education institutions and scientific-research institutes in Georgia.

[Workshop on Gender Equality in Research in the Horizon Europe funding scheme](#)

Date: 2 February 2022 | Location: Online | Partner: ECE-NTUA

On February 2nd 2022 ECE-NTUA organised a workshop in collaboration with the PRAXI Network, a unit of the Foundation for Research & Technology – Hellas (FORTH). The title of the event was 'Funding opportunities from the "Reforming & Enhancing the EU R&I System" programme & presentation of the EU funded project CALIPER: Gender Equality in STEM Research'. In the context of this workshop, the CALIPER team of ECE-NTUA presented the topic of Gender Equality in Research in the Horizon Europe funding scheme. They also talked about the Gender Equality Plan they are implementing in their School.

["The invisibilisation/invisibility of women in Science, Technology, Mathematics and Engineering. A dialogue with the Human and Social Sciences"](#)

Date: 11 February 2022 | Location: Brussels, Belgium | Partner: ULB

For the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11 February 2022), ULB's CALIPER team organised the conference «The invisibilisation/invisibility of women in Science, Technology, Mathematics and Engineering. A dialogue with the Human and Social Sciences» in collaboration with [STRIGES](#), ULB's interdisciplinary research structure on gender and sexuality. The conference addressed the question of the lack of visibility and/or presence of women in STEM disciplines by looking at both high school students' gendered attitudes towards science and technology and the barriers women face in STEM careers. The speakers come from both STEM and SHS in order to promote interdisciplinary dialogue. This conference took place within the opening day of the multidisciplinary exhibition [F.A.S.T. Femmes Arts Sciences Technologies](#), organised by [Ohme](#) in collaboration with CALIPER and many other partners from 11 February to 6 March 2022 at ULB's premises. The exhibition aimed at shedding light, from a historical and artistic point of view, on the *invisibilisation* of women in the history of art, science, and technology.

[Online workshop CALIPER H2020: Discussion on Equal Opportunities and Preparation of Gender Equality Plans](#)

Date: 28 May 2022 | Location: Online | Partner: STU BA

On May 28th, STU BA organised an online workshop for external stakeholders of the R&I Hub. The participants discussed the need for equal opportunities in research and innovation and the role of the Gender Equality Plans. The GEP of STU BA was presented by the CALIPER team. The meeting was divided into two blocks of questions focusing on the level of awareness of the participants and their advice in terms of important topics to be addressed.

3.4.5 CALIPER in external events

During this reporting period, the CALIPER partners participated in 9 external events. A short description of them can be found below:

[Gender summit: Gender Equality, Diversity, Inclusion post-Corona: Quo vadis?](#)

Date: 14-16 April 2021 | Location: Online | Partner: YAE

Dr. Mangala Srinivas, CSO of Cenya Imaging and former Chair of our project partners, [YAE](#), participated in the [Gender summit: Gender Equality, Diversity, Inclusion post-Corona: Quo vadis?](#) By presenting the career pathways and professional preparations of PhD holders. Among others, Dr. Srinivas presented the goals and vision of the CALIPER project which is to make research organisations more gender-equal by increasing the number of female researchers in STEM, improving their career prospects, and integrating a gender dimension in research.

[Gender Policies in Scientific Institutions: CERCA-URUGUAY](#)

Date: 5 May 2021 | Location: Online | Partner: IRB

CALIPER partner IRB contributed to the online event Gender Policies in Scientific Institutions: CERCA-URUGUAY held on the 5th of May 2021 organised by CERCA-URUGUAY. Dr. Neus Prats Costa and Marcelo Mora from IRB participated in the online session. A presentation titled: Gender Policies in Scientific Institutions was held presenting the CALIPER project, the project partner, and its objectives.

[Workshop: Women in Science](#)

Date: 28 May 2021 | Location: Online | Partner: UZG-FER

The workshop “Women in Science” was held aimed at promoting EU horizontal principles with a focus on gender equality. The workshop was open to all interested parties. Women in Engineering Croatia – WIE was one of the co-organisers of this event, and during the workshop, WIE activities in relation to the CALIPER project were presented. WIE represents a group of IEEE members who have recognised and joined the IEEE’s efforts to inspire, engage, encourage and strengthen the professional and social engagement of women – engineers and scientists – around the world.

[Annual meeting of the Romanian Rectors](#)

Date: 10 October 2021 | Location: Braşov, Romania | Partner: UEFISCDI

The National Council of Rectors (CNR) met between 08-10.20.2021 at the Transilvania University of Braşov, in a working meeting. Along with the representatives of the universities, were the Minister of Education - Mr. Sorin Mihai Cîmpeanu, as well as representatives of other bodies and institutions involved in higher education. Considering the agenda of the meeting and the complex topics under debate, the National Council of Rectors adopted some measures regarding the increase of the performance and competitiveness of the national system of higher education and scientific research, as well as the structure and manner of CNR meetings. During this meeting the UEFISCDI team had the opportunity to present the development process of their GEP.

[EC GEP facility training \(Greece\)](#)

Date: 9 November 2021 | Location: Online | Partner: ECE-NTUA

The CALIPER team at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the NTUA was invited to present the lessons learned from the development of the School's GEP, at a training session organised by the European Commission, on November 9, 2021. The online training was a part of the support activities provided to organisations across Europe on complying with the [GEP eligibility criterion](#) in Horizon Europe.

The training sessions are targeting EU Member States and Associated Countries in which there are many organisations affected by the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion which do not have a GEP in place yet. The training session aimed at supporting stakeholders in Greece and was attended by 33 representatives from academic institutions, research organisations, and public sector stakeholders. During the meeting the CALIPER team presentation addressed the key lessons from the process of developing the Gender Equality Plan as part of the CALIPER project. The presentation highlighted the CALIPER project, the internal assessment methodology, as well as the contents of the School's GEP. Finally, the presentation reported on various observations and best practices involving the development of the plan and provided a set of recommendations.

[WomIn Tech event](#)

Date: 11 November 2021 | Location: Brussels, Belgium | Partner: ULB

On November 11th 2021, our colleague Sara Aguirre from ULB participated in the event "Reducing Gender Bias in STEM: Strategies and Actions", a round table organised by the students' association [WomIn Tech](#). During the round table, the speakers discussed with students of the Polytechnic School of ULB about gender bias in education and in the workplace, and solutions in enterprises, universities and schools.

[EC GEP facility training \(Croatia\)](#)

Date: 12 December 2021 | Location: Online | Partner: UZG-FER

The CALIPER team at the Faculty of [Electrical Engineering and Computing of UZG](#) was invited to present the lessons learned from the development of the Faculty's GEP, in a training session organised by the European Commission, on December 12, 2021. The online training was a part of the support activities provided to organisations across Europe on complying with the [GEP eligibility criterion](#) in Horizon Europe. The training is targeting the EU Member States and Associated Countries in which there are many organisations affected by the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion which do not have a GEP in place yet. The training session included presentations on aspects of the design and development of a GEP and the relevant eligibility criterion for Horizon Europe.

The CALIPER team presentation addressed the key lessons from the process of developing the Gender Equality Plan as part of the CALIPER project. The presentation highlighted the CALIPER project, the internal assessment methodology, as well as the contents of the School's GEP. Finally, the presentation reported on various observations and best practices involving the development of the plan and provided a set of recommendations.

[Global Women's Breakfast – Romania 2022](#)

Date: 16 February 2022 | Location: Online | Partner: UEFISCDI

On February 16th, UEFISCDI participated in the Global Women's Breakfast – Romania 2022. The National Research-Development Institute for Chemistry and Petrochemistry – ICECHIM Bucharest organised the first event of the IUPAC Global Women's Breakfast series in Romania and invites all interested parties to join the initiative to support diversity in research.

The event aimed to celebrate the achievements of women in science and inspire young generations to pursue a career in research, as well as to celebrate together the UN International Day of Women and Girls in Science. During the webinar, UEFISCDI presented the development of the GEP and the start of the implementation phase and at the Q&A UEFISCDI responded to many questions regarding the steps needed in the development of a GEP.

The event was held online, and it was attended by 94 people, 71 females and 23 males.

[EC GEP facility training \(Romania\)](#)

Date: 25 March 2022 | Location: Online | Partner: UEFISCDI

The CALIPER team at the [Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania](#) was invited to present the lessons learned from the development of the institution's GEP, in a training session organised by the European Commission, on March 25, 2022. The online training was a part of the support activities provided to organisations across Europe on complying with the [GEP eligibility criterion](#) in Horizon Europe. The training is targeting the EU Member States and Associated Countries in which there are many organisations affected by the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion which do not have a GEP in place yet. The training session included presentations on aspects of the design and development of a GEP and the relevant eligibility criterion for Horizon Europe.

The CALIPER team presentation addressed the key lessons from the process of developing the Gender Equality Plan as part of the CALIPER project. The presentation highlighted the CALIPER project, the internal assessment methodology, as well as the contents of the School's GEP. Finally, the presentation reported on various observations and best practices involving the development of the plan and provided a set of recommendations.

[ECORYS webinar on Gender Equality Plans in the R&I sector](#)

Date: 27 April 2022 | Location: Online | Partner: IRB

On 27th April 2022, our partner IRB participated in the webinar organised by [ECORYS](#) on the topic of Gender Equality Plans in the R&I sector. The CALIPER team of IRB and the project coordinator Kyriaki Karydou had the opportunity to present CALIPER to a diverse audience and talk about the importance of gender equality in the STEM field. Also, Marcelo Mora from IRB presented the IRB experience of implementing their GEP. ECORYS is active in the sectors of social policy, regional development, transport and infrastructure, security and justice, natural resources, economic growth, and public sector reform.

3.5 Promotion through partners' network

CALIPER benefits from the partners' already established community of followers and social media channels to further disseminate the project and its activities. Partners reshare the communication material created by the communication manager or produce their own, enabling the project to expand its visibility and outreach. All project partners put efforts into communicating CALIPER activities through their social media channels and official websites.

3.5.1 Website

All RPOs/RFOs that implement a GEP host a dedicated page on their official websites to inform their visitors about the project and its actions. Also, they use hyperlinks to direct the users to the CALIPER website or the

project’s social media accounts. The partners share news about the project on their website, mostly about their achievements as implementing partners. Examples of the partners’ websites can be found below:

UZG-FER

Održana radionica Rodno osjetljivo poučavanje u STEM-u ^{novo}

Izv. prof. dr. sc. Pina Milišić, nastavnica Zavoda za primijenjenu matematiku te predsjednica interesne skupine IEEE Žene u inženjerstvu, održala je radionicu *Rodno osjetljivo poučavanje u STEM-u* u petak 13. svibnja 2022. Radionica je organizirana u sklopu provedbe Plana ravnopravnosti spolova FER-a i projekta Caliper.

Na predavanju je dan osvrt na važnost kreativnosti u područjima STEM-a te važnost individualiziranih pristupa studentima s ciljem razvoja kreativnosti u struci. Nakon pregleda izazova u nastavi STEM-a, sudionici su radili na razvoju nastavnih jedinica koje potiču i osnažuju studenata za poslove budućnosti.

U radionici su sudjelovali nastavnici Sveučilišta u Zagrebu, Tehničkog veleučilišta u Zagrebu, Algebre i poduzeća STEMI.

SRNSFG

27 May, 2022

Within the framework of CALIPER project: Linking Research and Innovation for Gender Equality, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia implemented significant structural changes

Within the framework of CALIPER project: Linking Research and Innovation for Gender Equality, Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia implemented significant structural changes. As result of previously elaborated Gender Equality Plan, that includes various planned activities targeting different areas of intervention, few GEP activities related to Human Resources and Institutional Governance areas were implemented. Particularly, the beginning of first iteration phase included activities such as, elaboration of the informational brochure/guide for recruited staff about gender equality, the development of exit questionnaire for staff, collecting gender disaggregated data at the institutional level and modification of existing job descriptions in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender related issues in the organization. All of the activities were successfully implemented and in long-term perspective.

IRB

At IRB Barcelona we have a Plan

INSTITUTIONAL 24 NOV 21

In the 21st century, you might think that an international research centre like IRB Barcelona does not need measures to guarantee equality and diversity. However, the reality is that we still have a way to go to ensure more diverse, equitable, and inclusive science. Ending inequalities and discrimination based on gender or other social identities in biomedical research is a milestone that we want to help achieve.

Last year, within the framework of CALIPER Project and supported by the Equality and Diversity Committee and a team of internal and external collaborators, the project work team evaluated a range of aspects associated with equality. In this regard, the evaluation covered areas related to governance, human resources, communication, research, harassment, and intersectionality.

After a few months of working with a variety of approaches, including an internal study, focus groups, surveys, and interviews, it has been concluded that some areas require improvement, and 24 actions have been drawn up in this regard.

The 24 actions are framed within the aforementioned areas. Examples include the development of an **inclusive language guide**, a **work-life balance guide**, the updating of the **harassment protocol**, the maintenance and improvement of **mentoring programmes** and training sessions on the **inclusion of the gender dimension in research**. These actions have been validated at the institutional level by all the parties necessary for their successful implementation.

To begin with, one of the first actions of the **Gender Equality Plan** in the coming months is to inform the IRB Barcelona community about it in depth. For the plan to be successful, all members of the Institute must be engaged with it and embrace it, thus allowing its fruits to be reaped over the next four years.

Through an official online presentation of the 2021-2025 Gender Equality Plan on 24 November, followed by a round table on mentoring, we want to make the plan (which you will definitely be hearing more about over the next 4 years) known.

PARTICIPANTS

- **MARIBEL LABRID**
Head of Human Resources and Academic Affairs
- **DR. NEUS PRATS**
Core Facility Manager
Histopathology Facility
- **SÓNIA SABORIT**
Section Head Pre-Award Grants
- **DR. MARIA J. MACIAS**
Group Leader
Structural Characterization of Macromolecular Assemblies
- **MARTINA GASULL**

UEFISCDI

GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

About the project | Proposed measures | Models | Romania

Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in UEFISCDI

Partner in the EU-funded [CALIPER](#) project, UEFISCDI is the first public institution in Romania to undertake the elaboration and implementation of a Gender Equality Plan (GEP).

Proposed measures | Read more ↓

Developed with the help of CALIPER project partners and using the methodology proposed in the project consortium, UEFISCDI's Gender Equality Plan was elaborated based on the results of a

UNILE

"GENDER EQUALITY PLAN": UNISALENTO ADOTTA UN PIANO PER L'UGUAGLIANZA DI GENERE

14 Marzo 2022 | Redazione | UNIVERSITÀ E RICERCA

UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO

Presentazione il 16 marzo 2022 in presenza in Rettorato e online

L'Università del Salento ha adottato un "Piano per l'uguaglianza di genere", un cosiddetto "GEP - Gender Equality Plan", che definisce la strategia dell'Ateneo per ridurre le disuguaglianze di genere e valorizzare le diversità e che verrà applicato da quest'anno e fino al 2025.

Il piano verrà presentato **mercoledì 16 marzo 2022** alle ore 9.30 nella sala conferenze del Rettorato (piazza Tancredi 7, Lecce): sarà possibile partecipare in presenza prenotandosi su <https://www1.unisalento.it/uguaglianza-genero> o seguire online collegandosi su <https://unisalento.it/160322>.

Apriranno i lavori il Rettore **Fabio Pollice** e il Direttore generale **Donato De Benedetto**; presenterà il GEP la Delegata alle Politiche di genere **Anna Maria Cherubini**. Interverranno quindi il Delegato alla Ricerca **Alessandro Sannino** e la Coordinatrice del Progetto Caliper **Rosaria Rinaldi**. Ospiti della giornata saranno **Silvia Ghiselli**, Responsabile dell'Ufficio Statistico di Alma Laurea, che presenterà alcune "Considerazioni sulle carriere di laureati e laureate dall'osservatorio di Alma Laurea", e la Responsabile dell'Agenda di Genere della Regione Puglia **Titti De Simone**, che parlerà di "Ricerca e formazione nell'agenda di genere della Regione Puglia: prospettive e sinergie". Modererà l'incontro la Presidente del CUG - Comitato Unico di Garanzia dell'Ateneo **Monica Mc Britton**.

Nel corso della presentazione verrà annunciata l'istituzione di un **premio di tesi di dottorato** rivolto alle dottorande UniSalento.

«Con l'adozione del GEP UniSalento recepisce pienamente le raccomandazioni della Commissione Europea, che indica questo strumento come misura fondamentale per promuovere l'uguaglianza di genere nella ricerca e nell'innovazione e che lo pone come requisito di accesso ai finanziamenti del programma di ricerca Horizon Europe», spiega la professoressa **Anna Maria Cherubini**, Delegata del Rettore alle Politiche di genere e coordinatrice del gruppo che ha messo a punto il GEP, «Per la

Table 6 CALIPER on partners' websites

3.5.2 Social media

The CALIPER consortium promotes the project and its activities through their social media accounts as well. The posts revolve around the RPOs/RFOs activities in the context of CALIPER, and also the social media campaigns the project organises or participates in. Sample posts can be found below:

Vilabs.eu @vilabs_eu · Jun 2

🔗 Το έργο @CaliperEu παρουσιάζει το #rolemodel video με την καθηγήτρια Ασμίνα Κιούρτη από το παν/μιο της πολιτείας του Οχάιο. Μας μίλησε για την καριέρα της στις θετικές επιστήμες & το όραμά της για τις γυναίκες στην έρευνα & την καινοτομία

👤 @DSS_Lab 🗣️

youtube.com
Role model interview - Assist. Prof. Asimina Kiourti...
CALIPER is a Project that supports 9 Research Organisations across Europe to develop Gender ...

🗨️ 🔄 ❤️ 2 📤 📺

CU

Academia Europaea Cardiff @acardiff · May 24

📺 Our next @CaliperEu #RoleModel video is out!

Meet Prof Asimina Kiourti, Wearable & Implantable Technologies #research lead at @ElectroSciOSU as she encourages young women to reach out to others in #STEM

Watch the video: bit.ly/3lFHjSI
#WomenSupportingWomen #WomenInSTEM

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

1:57 349 views

🗨️ 🔄 1 ❤️ 3 📤

SRNSFG

შოთა რუსთაველის საქართველოს ეროვნული სამეცნიერო ფონდი February 11 · 🌐

Caliper EU
#caliperu #SRNSFG
#მეცნიერქალთადაგოგონათასაერთაშორისოდღე

See Translation

CALIPER წარმოადგენს პროექტს, რომელიც ითვალისწინებს მეცნიერ ქალთა და გოგონათა ჩართულობას STEM-ის მიმართულებებში. კენდერული თანასწორობის აღმოსაფხვრელად, ასევე გენდერული სტერეოტიპებისა და მიკერძობულობის შესახებ დისკუსიის წარმართვის მიზნით მუშაობდა კენდერული თანასწორობის გეგმა.

11/02/22 ეს არის დღე ჩვენი ძალების მობილიზაციისთვის!

მეცნიერ ქალთა და გოგონათა საერთაშორისო დღე

👍❤️ You and 52 others 2 Comments 2 Shares

ULB

ECE-NTUA

IRB

[YAE Newsletter | YAE, AE Cardiff Hub and CALIPER will host a panel on ESOF 2022](#)

[SAPEA Newsletter | CALIPER role model features in SAPEA newsletter](#)

[AE Newsletter | AE Cardiff welcomes new CALIPER communication officer](#)

[AE Newsletter | Cardiff Hub joins European project to improve gender equality in research](#)

[YAE Newsletter | CALIPER interviews with role models in STEM](#)

[FER Newsletter | Announcement of the GEP in the UZG-FER newsletter \(Croatian\)](#)

[YAE Newsletter | CALIPER Survey: The impact of the Pandemic on Early-Career Researchers](#)

[YAE Newsletter | CALIPER Role Model interview with Prof. Ivana Podnar Žarko](#)

[UZG FER | Announcement of the WIN event in the FER newsletter](#)

Figure 24 CALIPER on partners' newsletters

3.6 The EU Sister Projects initiative

The EU funded projects that work on gender equality have joined forces and created the [EU Sister Projects](#) network with the #EUSisterProjects. The purpose of this sisterhood is to facilitate the exchange of ideas and experiences, as well as the engagement of external key players, by organising and participating in networking activities. The sister projects work together to organise events, campaigns and other activities. At this point

there are 31 projects and initiatives in the EU Sister Projects (including CALIPER) listed on the CALIPER website. With most of these projects, CALIPER collaborated in various social media campaigns.

Figure 25 The EU Sister projects

3.6.1 Synergy activities

In this section there are all the synergy activities among the EU Sister Projects.

1. Social Media Campaigns

The sister projects are very active on social media and they often organise joint campaigns to raise awareness around the topics of gender equality. During this reporting period, CALIPER participated in five common campaigns.

[Campaign #BeOpenAboutPay](#)

Date: 18 September 2021 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [SPEAR](#), [GRANteD](#)

On the International Equal Pay Day on the 18th of September the sister projects organised the campaign #BoOpenAboutPay and reflected upon salary transparency by asking their participating RPO/RFOs to #BeOpenAboutPay and share the existence of relevant policies on pay transparency at a national level. The pictures below show some of the posters that were shared by CALIPER using the content provided by the CALIPER partners.

Figure 26 #BeOpenAboutPay material

Campaign #SafeResearch4All

Date: 25 November 2021 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [UniSAFE](#), [GEARING-Roles](#), [SPEAR](#), [SUPERA](#), [GENDERTARGET](#), [RESET](#), [TARGETED-MPI](#)

The CALIPER project, on the occasion of the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women on November 25th, joined the #SafeResearch4All campaign organised by the sister projects to raise awareness on gender-based violence in research and academia. Examples of the posts are featured below.

Figure 27 #SafeResearch4All material

[Campaigns #ChristmasWishes4Equality & #NewYearWishes4Equality](#)

Date: December 2021 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [GEARING-Roles](#), [SPEAR](#), [R&I Peers](#), [UniSAFE](#), [EQUALS-EU](#), [RESISTIRE](#), [GE-Academy](#), [GENDER-Smart](#)

On the occasion of the Christmas holidays the sister projects organised the campaigns #ChristmasWishes4Equality & #NewYearWishes4Equality with GEARING-Roles leading and wished for a more gender equal and diverse STEM community, and for all Research & Innovation institutions to have a Gender Equality Plan. CALIPER actively participated in the campaign by posting relevant content on its social media accounts.

Figure 28 #ChristmasWishes4Equality/#NewYearWishes4Equality

Campaign #DreamItBelt

Date: 11 February 2022 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [GenPORT](#), [GRANteD](#), [SUPERA](#), [SPEAR](#), [ATHENA](#), [ACT](#), [CASPER](#), [RESET](#), [Equal4Europe](#), [LeTSGEPs](#), [MINDtheGEPs](#), [GEARING-Roles](#), [GENDER-Smart](#), [GenderSTI](#).

On the International Day for Women and Girls in Science, on February 11th, the CALIPER project took the initiative to organise a campaign under #DreamItBelt. The campaign was a joint effort from 15 sister projects. In this regard, within the context of this campaign the projects shared inspirational stories from female researchers. The posts revolved around three main questions:

- *What is your professional background?*
- *What did inspire you to pursue this career?*
- *Who was your role model?*

The female researchers had the opportunity to share their experiences and journeys. Some examples are presented below.

Figure 29 #DreamItBeIt material

On the same occasion, CALIPER further involved the RPOs/RFOs in the consortium, and asked them to give tips on how they attract women and girls to STEM. Some examples of this material can be found below:

Figure 30 #DreamItBelt material from CALIPER partners

Campaign on the International Women Day #IWD2022

Date: 8 March 2022 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [GENDERACTION](#), [R&I Peers](#), [RESISTIRE](#), [GENDERTARGET](#), [UniSAFE](#), [CASPER](#), [RESET](#), [Equal4Europe](#), [LeTSGEPs](#), [MINDtheGEPs](#), [GEARING-ROLES](#), [GenderSTI](#), [GRANteD](#), [SUPERA](#), [SPEAR](#), [ATHENA](#), [ACT](#), [GENDER-smart](#).

On the occasion of International Women’s Day on March 8th, the Sister Projects organised a campaign to demonstrate their valuable contribution to promoting Gender Equality in Research and Innovation. The projects created a thread on Twitter under the “[mother](#)” tweet of the European Research Executive Agency. Each sister project created relevant material to display its vision and ambition for a more gender equal research community and society in general.

Figure 31 #IWD material

Figure 32 #IWD CALIPER partners' material

2. Online and offline events

When the sister projects organise events, they invite other projects to participate as speakers or co organisers to increase the outreach and impact of the event. During this reporting period there were 5 sister events that CALIPER participated in.

[ATHENA's training for the GEP committees](#)

Date: November 2021 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [ATHENA](#)

Representatives from ULB, the Belgian CALIPER partner, took part in the training, offered by the sister project ATHENA: Institutional change and gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe. The training included two lectures, under four learning objectives:

- Familiarise participants with the main concepts of gender equality and understanding its rationale
- Acquire skills to promote and lead change management
- Introduce the ATHENA project approach for institutional change
- Developing knowledge on key aspects and basic steps to develop and implement gender equality

[CALIPER scientific coordinator Maria Sanguiliano summarises the caliper experience](#)

Date: December 2021 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [SUPERA](#)

The CALIPER scientific coordinator Maria Sanguiliano talked to the sister project SUPERA, about how CALIPER addresses the dimensions of inclusivity. The [H2020 CALIPER project](#) was designed and is now implemented, since 2020, having multisectoriality as its key specific feature to be embedded in all steps of the institutional change process, from the internal assessment to the GEPs design and implementation phases, as well as in monitoring and evaluation.

[Webinar: "Engaging with external stakeholders and innovation ecosystems to foster institutional change"](#)

Date: 8 April 2022 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [SUPERA](#), [GENDER-Smart](#)

CALIPER along with the sister project GENDER-Smart, took part in our other sister SUPERA webinar "Engaging with external stakeholders and innovation ecosystems to foster institutional change" while implementing a Gender Equality Plan. The CALIPER scientific coordinator Maria Sanguiliano presented the CALIPER methodology and reflected on the adoption of new indicators for assessing gender inequalities taking into account areas of collaboration between research organisations and their innovation ecosystem, and codesigning Gender Equality Plans.

[Panel discussion "Everyone's business: gender equality and the context of higher education"](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Date: 10 June 2022 | Location: Online | Involved project(s): [SPEAR](#)

CALIPER partner UZG-FER participated in the SPEAR panel discussion on gender mainstreaming in academia. During the panel discussion the speakers talked about how promoting gender equality, was further strengthened in early 2022, after the establishment of the GEP eligibility criterion. This should be preceded by the implementation of preliminary research on gender equality at the institution that intends to adopt the GEP.

[4th Summit on Gender Equality in Computing \(GEC'22\)](#)

Date: 16-17 June 2022 | Location: Thessaloniki, Greece (hybrid) | Involved project(s): [RESET](#), [Gearing-Roles](#), [UniSAFE](#), [EUGAIN](#), [ATHENA](#), [LeTSGEPs](#), [GenderSTI](#)

In the context of the 4th Summit on Gender Equality in Computing (GEC'22), RESET organised the workshop "ACT TOGETHER", and invited the EU Sister Projects to participate. During the workshop, the projects had the opportunity to talk about the impact of their activities on their environments, and their work in combating stereotypes and biases in the STEM field. From the CALIPER part, the project coordinator Kyriaki Karydou and the colleagues Maria Flouri (ECE-NTUA) and Marcelo Mora (IRB) presented the efforts and impact on their organisations.

Figure 33 ACT together event

3.6.2 CALIPER promoted by external stakeholders

The projects participating in the EU Sister Projects network, enhance the visibility of each other, using their communication channels. In this regard, the projects share news about other projects in the network, using their websites and social media accounts. Also, CALIPER has been mentioned by EU level stakeholders such as the Horizon Europe account. Sample posts of these promotional activities are displayed below.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Figure 34 External stakeholders promoting CALIPER on social media

Figure 35 External stakeholders promoting CALIPER on their websites

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4 KPIs and monitoring

The monitoring and evaluation of the CALIPER dissemination activities is an essential task that is performed regularly, to provide concrete evidence on the effectiveness of dissemination, as well as insights on how to maximise its reach and impact. Specific KPIs have been developed from the beginning of the project to allow comparisons between the planned and actual activities, as well as their effectiveness to reach their goals. The table below summarised the KPIs relevant to this task and the project's performance so far.

Channel	Tool	KPI	This period	Total number for the period M1-M30
Media	Press release	Total of 25	2	15
Online channels	Website	Take website live featuring information about the project and update the content periodically	The website is constantly being updated with CALIPER news and activities.	N/A
	Project publications	At least 3 publications per year.	7	38 publications (deliverables, internal/external assessments, articles, presentations)
	Newsletter	1 Issue every 6 months.	2	5
	Social media	Total of 1,000 followers.	153 new followers	1,402 in total
Offline activities	Promotion materials (brochures, posters, etc.)	Create project's brochure and prepare more materials according to project's needs.	Textbook, pen and Linen bag (SRNSFG WIN event)	
	Conference presentations	>10 presentations along the project	17	22
	Collaboration with other EU funded projects/initiatives	>4 collaborations	10	20

Table 8 CALIPER KPIs

5 Conclusion

The present report provides a comprehensive overview of CALIPER Consortium's effort to disseminate and communicate the project to the internal as well as external target audiences. It provides an overview of all the online and offline communication and dissemination activities of the project during the respective period, as well as the updates in the communication tools. The reported period was M16-M30 (April 2021 – June 2022). The documented activities have been clustered according to the type of the actions (events, communication material, social media etc). This way, the current deliverable demonstrates continuity and provides evidence necessary to the planning of the future actions of project dissemination and communication.

Some key points of this report include:

- Overall achievement of the KPIs so far
- Increased traffic in the campaign periods in all the communication channels
- Wide dissemination of the project through the participation of the RPOs/RFOs in external events.

All in all, the expected achievements of the period have been reached. The efforts managed to achieve more than expected and created a strong network of the CALIPER followers. For the next reporting period which covers the months from July 2022 until December 2023 the focus will be on further disseminating the events and activities of the partners. The next steps can be summarised as follow:

- Continuation of the overall dissemination and communication activities
- Completion of the RPOs/RFOs pages on the CALIPER website
- Further promotion of the website through social media
- Efforts to engage users from the consortium countries with less reach
- Support of the T5.4 and the sustainability actions, to attract more external key stakeholders to the relevant activities.

This deliverable is the interim version of the Dissemination and Communication activities. The final version will be delivered at the end of the project in M48 (December 2023).

